

M. Mazur, J. H. Kwah, T. Indlekofer, J. R. Dawson, N. A. Worth, *Self-excited longitudinal and azimuthal modes in a pressurised annular combustor*, Proc. Combust. Inst. 38, 2021

Supplemental material

Acoustic characterisation

The acoustic boundary conditions between the sintered metal plate and the injection tubes were determined using the multi-microphone-method [2]. Acoustic forcing was applied on a single injection tube and two microphones were used to characterise the magnitude of incoming and reflected pressure waves and therefore the reflective coefficient of the inlet boundary. A loudspeaker was mounted at the top of the injector tube and a frequency sweep from 100 Hz to 2500 Hz was conducted.

The reflective coefficient of the upstream boundary is calculated by $R_{in} = (H_{31} - e^{-ik_i s}) / (e^{-ik_r s} - H_{31}) e^{-i(k_i + k_r)(x_1 - x_s)}$, with $H_{31} = \hat{p}_3 / \hat{p}_1$ the transfer function between the measured pressure in position 1 and 3, calculated in Fourier space. $x_s = 189$ mm is the position of the sinter metal plate relative to the combustor dump plane and $s = x_3 - x_1$ is the distance between the two pressure sensors. k_i and k_r describe the wave number ω/c of the incident and reflected waves respectively.

The reflection coefficient magnitude and phase are plotted in figure. S1. The reflection coefficient magnitude is shown to decrease with increasing frequencies, taking values of $|R_{in}| \leq 0.5$ over the frequency range of interest. Therefore, while improving flow uniformity and operability of the experiment, the sintered plate may also be responsible for a significant amount of damping.

Based on an estimate of combustor Mach number, a downstream reflection coefficient $R_{out} = 0.999$ can be estimated based on Marble et al. [1] suggesting a close to fully reflective condition.

Figure S1: Modulus and phase of the reflective coefficient at the boundary between the sintered metal plate and injector tubes.

Sintered metal plate properties

The sintered metal plate (SIKA B-100 from GKN) is made of brass and has a porosity of 0.12, a thickness

of $s = 22$ mm, a mean pore size of $183 \mu\text{m}$ and an inner and outer diameter of 130 mm and 206 mm respectively.

The pressure drop through the plate is calculated by $\Delta p = (\dot{V} s \nu) / (A \alpha)$ [3], with \dot{V} the volume flow rate, ν the dynamic viscosity, A the surface and $\alpha = 127 \cdot 10^{-12} \text{ m}^2$ a material specific constant. Assuming a constant dynamic viscosity of $\nu = 20 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ Pa}\cdot\text{s}$ (which is accurate in the studied pressure range), the pressure drop thus increases linearly with the volume flow rate and evolves between 12.9 kPa and 16 kPa. The pressure drop for the different mass flow rates in the present investigation is shown in figure S2.

Figure S2: Pressure drop of the sintered metal plate at different volume flow rates.

- [1] F. E. Marble, S. M. Candel, Acoustic disturbance from gas non-uniformities convected through a nozzle. J. Sound Vibr. 55 (1977) 225–243.
- [2] J. Y. Chung, D. A. Blaser, Transfer function method of measuring induct acoustic properties. I. Theory. J. Acoust. Soc. Am. 68 (1980) 907–913.
- [3] GKN, Filter-Elements High porosity sintered parts SIKA-R...AX and SIKA-B (2018).